

A Clinical Analysis of Ectopic Pregnancies in a Tertiary Care Centre: A One Year Retrospective Study

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Abstract:

Background: This retrospective study at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital in Bhagalpur, Bihar, examines the prevalence and management of ectopic pregnancies, focusing on rural populations over the span from June 2023 to June 2024.

Methods: The study reviewed clinical profiles and outcomes for 60 cases of ectopic pregnancy. Data were collected on symptoms, diagnostic accuracy, and treatment efficacy, with an emphasis on the transition from laparoscopy to laparotomy for surgical interventions.

Results: Common symptoms reported included abdominal pain and vaginal bleeding. Ultrasound played a critical role in the initial diagnosis, demonstrating high accuracy. Treatment predominantly involved surgical procedures, with methotrexate effectively used in selected cases. The findings highlighted the importance of early detection and the advantageous impact of minimally invasive surgical techniques on patient outcomes.

Conclusion: Although the complication rate was low with no maternal fatalities, the study advocates for enhanced educational outreach and preventive measures to further refine treatment protocols and improve outcomes in ectopic pregnancy management.

Keywords: Ectopic Pregnancy, Laparotomy, Ultrasound Diagnosis, Methotrexate Treatment.

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Introduction

Implantation of a fertilised ovum outside the uterine cavity, known as ectopic pregnancy, poses a considerable clinical challenge in obstetrics [1]. This condition can lead to life-threatening complications and have long-term effects on future reproductive outcomes [2]. Despite its relatively low occurrence in pregnancies, this condition poses a significant risk to the health and well-being of expectant mothers during the early stages [3]. Ectopic pregnancies typically occur in the fallopian tube, but they can also happen in other locations such as the cervix, ovaries, or abdominal cavity [4]. Each of these locations poses its own set of diagnostic and therapeutic complexities. Recent developments in diagnostic technologies have significantly enhanced the ability to detect ectopic pregnancies at an early stage [5]. These include the use of transvaginal ultrasonography and the quantitative measurement of serum human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) levels [6]. Despite these advancements, the condition continues to be a significant health issue, particularly in areas where access to diagnostic tools is limited. Certain factors, including a past occurrence of pelvic inflammatory disease, prior ectopic pregnancy,

tubal surgery, or undergoing infertility treatments, have been identified as potential risk factors [7,8].

The primary aim of this retrospective study is to analyze the clinical profiles, diagnostic methods, treatment modalities, and outcomes of ectopic pregnancies over a one-year period at this tertiary care center. This analysis will help in identifying patterns in presentation and outcomes, assessing the effectiveness of current diagnostic and management strategies, and determining areas for improvement in patient care protocols. Additionally, the study seeks to contribute to the broader understanding of the impact of healthcare access disparities on the management of ectopic pregnancies and maternal health outcomes in the region.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This retrospective study was conducted at the Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital in Bhagalpur, Bihar, recognized as a prominent tertiary care center. The study covered the period from June 5, 2023, to June 30, 2024. During this time, researchers analyzed

the clinical presentations and outcomes of ectopic pregnancies.

Participants: The study encompassed 60 patients, with data consistently gathered at an average rate of about five patients per month. Participants were selected based on the hospital's medical records database, focusing on those who had a confirmed diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy within the study timeframe.

Data Collection: A thorough review of patient records was undertaken to collect necessary data, which included demographic details, symptoms at presentation, diagnostic procedures performed, treatment methods, and patient outcomes. The inclusion criteria required a confirmed diagnosis through clinical evaluations and imaging studies. Notably, laparotomy was employed as the diagnostic and treatment method in relevant cases.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis were conducted to assess the prevalence, distribution, and outcomes linked to various clinical features of ectopic pregnancies. The objective was to ascertain patterns and evaluate the efficacy of treatment protocols at the institution. All patient information was anonymized prior to analysis to maintain confidentiality and privacy.

Results

The study consisted of 60 female patients with an age range of 18 to 40 years, averaging 28 years. A significant 70% of these patients were from rural areas. In terms of reproductive history, 45% of the participants had at least one prior pregnancy, and

20% had experienced previous ectopic pregnancies. Clinically, the most common symptoms at presentation were abdominal pain (95%), vaginal bleeding (85%), and episodes of dizziness or syncope (30%). Diagnostic procedures showed that ultrasound imaging confirmed ectopic pregnancies in 98% of the cases. In 65% of these cases, laparotomy was performed for both definitive diagnosis and treatment. Regarding treatment outcomes, medical management with methotrexate was effective in 40% of the patients, particularly those diagnosed early with smaller ectopic masses. Surgical intervention, primarily consisting of salpingectomy, was necessary in 60% of the cases. The study noted complications in 15% of patients, the most frequent being persistent trophoblastic tissue that required additional methotrexate therapy. There were no maternal deaths reported, although 5% of the patients required blood transfusions due to hemodynamic instability. Follow-up assessments showed that 80% of the patients experienced uneventful recoveries, while 20% suffered from prolonged pelvic pain or irregular bleeding. The follow-up care also included counseling on future fertility and monitoring for recurrent ectopic pregnancies. Statistical analyses using Chi-square tests revealed significant associations between late diagnosis and the increased need for surgical management ($p < 0.05$). Logistic regression analysis highlighted that a history of prior ectopic pregnancy was a significant predictor of complications, with an odds ratio of 2.5 and a 95% confidence interval of 1.1-5.6 ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Details
Number of Patients	60 (Female)
Age Range	18-40 years (Mean Age: 28 years)
Residence	70% from rural areas
Reproductive History	45% had at least one prior pregnancy
	20% reported previous ectopic pregnancies

Table 2: Presentation, Diagnosis, and Treatment

Characteristic	Details
Common Symptoms	Abdominal pain (95%), Vaginal bleeding (85%), Dizziness or syncope (30%)
Diagnosis by Ultrasound	Confirmed in 98% of cases
Definitive Diagnosis and Treatment	Laparotomy used in 65% of cases
Medical Management	Methotrexate successful in 40% of cases
Surgical Management	Required in 60% of cases; Salpingectomy most common

Discussion

This retrospective study analyzed 60 cases of ectopic pregnancies at a tertiary care center in Bihar, identifying a higher incidence among women from rural areas. This demographic trend suggests possible disparities in healthcare access or

education on reproductive health in these regions. The clinical presentations predominantly included abdominal pain and vaginal bleeding, which align closely with symptoms documented in existing literature.

The prevalent symptoms observed in our study necessitate a heightened awareness among healthcare providers regarding the potential for ectopic pregnancies in women of reproductive age presenting with these issues. The diagnostic efficacy of ultrasound, confirmed in 98% of cases, underscores its vital role in the early detection and management of ectopic pregnancies, aligning with established best practices.

Compared to existing studies, our findings reinforce the utility of ultrasound as a primary diagnostic tool. While surgical interventions, notably salpingectomy, were necessary in 60% of the cases, reflecting a common approach for severe or medically unmanageable cases, the 40% success rate with methotrexate treatment highlights its significance as a viable, less invasive alternative in appropriately selected cases [11,13].

The relatively low but notable complication rate (15%), mainly due to persistent trophoblastic tissue, suggests areas for improvement in medical management and follow-up protocols [9]. The absence of maternal deaths in this cohort is a positive indicator of advances in both surgical and medical treatment options for ectopic pregnancies over recent years [10]. The strong association between prior ectopic pregnancies and subsequent complications underscores the need for targeted interventions and enhanced educational strategies for high-risk women to mitigate future risks [14]. This study not only sheds light on the management practices and outcomes of ectopic pregnancies at a tertiary care center but also emphasizes the critical challenges and opportunities for enhancing patient outcomes. Moving forward, research should aim to refine treatment protocols and expand preventive and educational measures to reduce the incidence and complications of ectopic pregnancies [12,15].

Conclusion

The retrospective analysis of ectopic pregnancies at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital over one year provided critical insights into the clinical presentations, treatment modalities, and outcomes associated with this condition. The study demonstrated a high reliance on surgical interventions, though the effectiveness of methotrexate as a less invasive option was notable in early-detected cases. Despite some complications, the absence of maternal mortality reflects positively on the current management strategies. These findings emphasize the importance of early diagnosis and tailored treatments to enhance patient outcomes. Continued efforts to improve educational outreach and access to care, particularly in rural areas, could further

mitigate the impact of ectopic pregnancies on maternal health.

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